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*Decoding of abbreviations in the process of translation*

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Modern English has a relatively new and highly productive way of word formation – abbreviation. The reduction itself, as a popular way of forming morphological neologisms in recent decades, reflects the tendency to rationalize language.

Continuous increase in the vocabulary of the language is a prerequisite for the rationalization of language, saving nominative and word-formation efforts. A striking example of the rationalization of speech activity and optimization of language-forming processes is the phenomenon of reduction of lexical units. In our information-rich world, there is less and less time for communication and correspondence. As paradoxical as it may sound, the more information a person has, the more ways he or she seeks to reduce and convey it in a concise form.

Abbreviation is a way of forming secondary nominative units, which develops under the influence of traditional ways of word formation. Therefore, according to these laws, such units are formed that transmit the greatest amount of information in a condensed and, at the same time, accessible form.

The term «abbreviation» refers to the process during which a word or phrase is abbreviated, and the abbreviated word itself. In addition, the terms «reduction process» and «abbreviated words» may be referred to as abbreviations, abbreviated units, abbreviated words, compound words, partially abbreviated words, acronyms, contractures, and ellipse.

Numerous works are devoted to certain aspects and classifications of Internet abbreviations in English and Ukrainian linguistics, as well as psycholinguistics: O. A Kirichenko, F. O Smirnov, L. M Chumak. V. V. Borisov determines the structure of abbreviations and their relationship with creative units, L. A Shelyakhovskaya and L. I Sapogova explore the basic principles of their modelling.

A large number of abbreviated units set an important task for the translator – to translate the abbreviation as adequately and clearly as possible, using all necessary methods and techniques. Abbreviations in translation should only be an encrypted language code that saves and optimizes language efforts.

Since English abbreviations can be attributed to the class of specific foreign names and words with unclear associative meaning, the process of their translation can be considered as a process of semantic adaptation.

To translate English abbreviations, you need to know the basic ways to transfer abbreviations into Ukrainian. Considering the process of translating abbreviations and acronyms, researchers first of all note that not only the translation, but also the decryption of the abbreviation in the original language always set significant difficulties for the reader or listener. This can be explained by the fact that there are many abbreviations that are not recorded in dictionaries, which are rarely used or are author's. When translating text with abbreviations

and acronyms, you should first refer to the dictionary. Each large dictionary has applications that form specific dictionaries, such as a dictionary of proper names, a dictionary of names and surnames and a dictionary of abbreviations and acronyms.

In any language of the world, the system of abbreviations is an integral part of its overall lexical and semantic system. That is why the systems of abbreviations in all languages are different.

The frequency of use of specific groups of abbreviations varies considerably, in particular in English e.g. (*Exempli gratia*), while in the Ukrainian language it is better to use in similar cases «*for example*». That is why you should not try to transfer foreign abbreviations during the translation in each case as well.

Sometimes an adequate translation is easy to choose depending on the context, but in addition to these meanings from different areas, abbreviations can have several meanings in one specific area. For example, the abbreviation CAT has several possible meanings on computer topics, such as: *computer-aided testing* (автоматизоване тестування), *computer-aided tomography* (комп'ютерна томографія), *computer-assisted training* (автоматизоване навчання) і *computeraided translation* (автоматизований переклад). Therefore, we can conclude that the context does not always unambiguously indicate the correct version of the translation.

The term «decoding» is usually understood as the process of establishing a derived word or correlate (unabridged form).

The following methods are used to decode abbreviations:

- context analysis;
- use of dictionaries of abbreviations;
- analysis of the structure of reductions;
- use of analogies.

Therefore, the process of translating absent abbreviations in dictionaries and reference books is carried out in two stages:

1) decoding the abbreviation, i.e identifying the original English form or correlate;

2) transmission of the correlate by means of the Ukrainian language, i.e the search for the appropriate Ukrainian form, which most accurately conveys the meaning of the identified concept.

Interest in studying the phenomenon of abbreviations in English has grown markedly. The choice of one or another method of translation depends on various factors. This is the nature of the translated text, and the audience of the consumer of products, and features of the psychology of the translator, his commitment to a particular literary tradition. It all depends on each case. The goals, objectives and conditions of interlingual professional communication play an important role in translation.